

Interview

[Speaker 2] (0:08 - 0:19)

So we are starting from the introduction, what is your name, company name and your position in the company?

[Speaker 1] (0:20 - 0:27)

Okay, so I'm Minan D'Souza, I work for SLB as a product champion for carbon storage operations.

[Speaker 2] (0:29 - 0:36)

Okay, now we are going to talk about the company. What are your roles and responsibilities in your position?

[Speaker 1] (0:37 - 2:31)

Okay, so as a product champion, which is the equivalent of a product manager in other companies [REDACTED]. So as a product manager, I have to basically provide the direction and vision for the product, the current product that we are developing is a product for carbon storage operations, so helping carbon storage operators manage their operations. They can use the tool to survey every part of the operations and report to the government and regulators how the operations are going.

And so my job is to work with the developers, the software developers and the project manager, to make sure the product is meeting the requirements that the client needs, and also that it's delivered at the right time, so that we can go to market with the best product possible, and also to manage the budget, the pricing of the product, and make sure that we are at a fair price. So those are my main responsibilities. Within the company, I also have responsibilities to mentor, in addition to my main job responsibilities, I have to make sure that I mentor technical experts because I'm a geoscientist by background, I have to make sure other geoscientists, that I'm spending some time to mentor them, the younger population, and train them, give guidance when they need, so that's my main job responsibility.

And my position, I forgot to mention at the start, is I'm part of the digital sustainability group in SLB, so we are a special division that builds products for sustainability.

[Speaker 2] (2:34 - 2:37)

Can you provide a brief history of the company?

[Speaker 1] (2:39 - 4:12)

Yes, so SLB, as you know, we recently changed names last year to SLB, we were formerly called Schlumberger, it's a global oilfield service and technology company that started in 1926, with two brothers that developed a tool that you could run in a well, that could image basically the earth, and give you some information about the rocks in the earth. So from that, almost 100 years now, next year is our 100 year anniversary, where we've kind of expanded to become the global leader in oilfield service and technology. Predominantly our main dominance is in drilling and production technology, and also reservoirs, reservoirs is the rocks, the subsurface, we're really good at providing digital technology for that as well.

And also today, in the last couple of years, we've also expanded our scope to include new energy, so we've created a whole new division called Schlumberger New Energy, that's sole aim is to provide low carbon energy solutions and digital services across energy sectors, renewable and oil and gas, so that's just a slight history, I think we have about 100,000 employees in 80-90 countries, something like that.

[Speaker 2] (4:13 - 4:16)

What is the company's mission and goals?

[Speaker 1] (4:17 - 6:12)

So, SLB's main mission is to create amazing technology that unlocks access to energy for the benefit of all, so that's our mission statement, but what it really means is we want to improve energy outcomes, because our main focus has been obviously oil and gas energy, which produces a lot of emissions, so what we've been trying to do is to improve that energy source, so to make it low carbon as much as possible, through technology, and also to help our customers reduce their emissions by making better technology.

And we're committed to achieving our net zero by 2050, we've made a strong commitment, and we also have targets for 2025 and 2030 that I'll tell you later. Our main goal is to decarbonize the oil and gas industry, to innovate in oil and gas to make it as efficient as possible so you can lower your emissions, to bring new energy systems, to bring new technology for new energy systems to the market, so we're also looking at, for example, hydrogen, geothermal, but we're also looking at how we can reduce emissions through carbon storage, for example, and that's where I'm contributing. We're trying to deliver digital at scale, so we're trying to get our digital technologies, we're obviously moving in the direction of digital technologies, because we think it's important to scale out and to be more efficient in energy in general. And on top of all of that, we also try to promote diversity and inclusion, so we make sure that we have, we're trying to have no gender pay gaps, gender equality in the company, and also, yeah, trying to have a diverse, we're trying to hire where we work so we don't move people across the world, so we have more locals in different offices.

So that's the goal.

[Redacted text block]

[Speaker 2] (6:34 - 6:41)

Okay, we are going to start about the second section, about stakeholders. Who are your main stakeholders?

[Speaker 1] (6:42 - 7:56)

So our main stakeholders are obviously customers that work in oil and gas sector in general, that's our main customer base, mostly international oil companies and national oil companies like ExxonMobil, Shell, Saudi Aramco, Petronas. So those are our main targets. We also now obviously cater to new energy companies, right, the geothermal companies and carbon storage operators.

Other stakeholders include suppliers and partners. We don't have technology across the entire value chain for all of the industry, so we work with suppliers and partners to achieve some parts of the supply chain. We also have investors, so obviously people who invest in the company, they have a vested interest in the company doing well.

Employees, the communities where operations are, obviously are affected by the operations, so they are stakeholders. And regulators, so government bodies that have regulations for oil and gas or energy in general. So those are our main stakeholders.

[Speaker 2] (7:57 - 8:02)

Among the stakeholders, who are the primary beneficiaries and contributors?

[Speaker 1] (8:03 - 9:04)

So the primary beneficiaries, so I assume that's the people that benefit from the operation, is the customers obviously. They get improved operations and they can lower their emissions. Shareholders, so obviously our shareholders get longer term value if the company has a better vision.

And the local communities, obviously they benefit from, can be both detrimental and beneficial, but local communities in general benefit from energy in their community, right. Contributors are typically employees like myself, the suppliers, the people that we work with, our partners that help us to produce our services and technology. Investors, who provide the funding we need to develop our technology.

And sometimes customers as well, because sometimes customers also give us a budget to produce technology.

[Speaker 2] (9:08 - 9:21)

Can we know what types of power or influence do these stakeholders contribute? For example, their respective interests, influence and interactions within the company.

[Speaker 1] (9:21 - 12:27)

Sure. So customers, they shape the product R&D obviously, because they are the primary stakeholders, right, of the technology. And also they work with us through contracting and joint projects sometimes.

So I would say that's how they influence us. They're the biggest influence on our technology and our roadmaps. Suppliers, they influence us either upstream or downstream, right, wherever they are working.

So they help us obviously to become more efficient, right, in operations. So they can help us also to be more compliant. So we have to make sure that we choose the right suppliers if we want to have our emissions goals met, right.

So suppliers can be very influential, especially in some parts of our value chain where they are very dominant, right. We need to make sure that they are working the same way as us. Investors and regulators.

So investors obviously influence us with capital allocation and strategy, right, because a lot of our budget comes from them, right. And they can provide the strategy in which direction they want us to develop technology, right. Regulators influence our customers predominantly, right.

So regulators will influence how a particular country is going after different types of energy sources. And so based on regulations, customers start to go after certain energy sources and then we are influenced by that, right. So in Norway, for example, where we are now, Norway is going after renewable energy a lot.

There's a lot of government regulations to go after new energy. So we are trying our best to match, right, to supply them with the technology they need for, you know, any of their new energy needs like wind or solar, stuff like that. So that's, yeah.

Communities we influence through, you know, basically community hiring, obviously. We hire locally. We try to have community programs.

So we do, we obviously work with universities, for example, for internships, for projects. We even, you know, provide our technology to the university for free. So my software, for example, I'll give free to the local university so that people can use it for projects, right, in the university.

We also try to have like water stewardship programs. We try to make sure that we're using less of the resources in our operations in the country that we operate, stuff like this. So that's how, yeah.

And they influence us by also, we have a lot of local communities that protest, right, when they are unhappy with the way we are operating. So they come and they protest and we try to hear them out, right, and see if there's a way, if there's really something we can do to keep the community happy, basically. Yeah.

[Speaker 2] (12:28 - 12:34)

How do these stakeholders use their power to affect your organization's value creation?

[Speaker 1] (12:35 - 15:04)

Yeah. So I kind of answered a bit of the question in the last thing, but I can say that a lot of customers, a lot of the oil and gas customers in the last few years have demand to go low carbon solutions, right? So because of that, because of the global push for net zero goals, right, to be met, many of them have had to diversify their energy sources.

And in order, some of them are very heavy oil and gas players, right, so for them, the best way for them to clean their emissions, right, to make sure that they reduce emissions

overall was to go after carbon storage, for example, right? So there was a massive push for many of our key customers to have carbon storage, and that's where, for example, our biggest funding for new energy is going right now because first, we could use the expertise we have in oil and gas. It's transferable to carbon storage, and we could also basically make an impact quickly.

So that's something that influenced us, for example, to create some, to go fast after CCS. Investors also, they influence us by, you know, they give us R&D. So they give us, they actually co-develop solutions with us.

So when they need solutions for technology that they don't have, right, they come to us because they don't want to develop the technology themselves. They don't have the resources. So they spend money with us, and they tell us what they need, but they make us develop the technology for them.

So that's how we create value together. And regulators, for example, can be very influential, right, like government bodies. They set compliance standards that companies have to meet, right, and then they ask for certain technologies to be deployed to make sure that you are reducing emissions as much as possible.

So a lot of the European governments have come in with very strict regulations about what technology can be used, and that's been also a lot of value creation for us, right, because they insist that you use good technology that reduces your emissions, and then we're one of the key suppliers of that, right? So that's how, you know, they affect our organization.

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[Speaker 2] (15:21 - 15:51)

[REDACTED]

Can you briefly explain what scope 1, 2, and 3 emission means?

[Speaker 1] (15:51 - 16:51)

Okay, so for us, scope 1 are the direct greenhouse gas emissions from operations we control, so fuel combustion on site, any of the generators we use on site, how much they produce emissions. Scope 2 is the indirect emissions from purchased electricity and heat. So, for example, you're in this building, any of the energy that we're using is coming from a third party, right?

So that's scope 2 emissions for us. Scope 3 is all the other indirect emissions across the value chain. So if they're using a supplier, their emissions count towards our scope 3.

If they're using a product, for example, if you use Microsoft, the emissions that they produce for that product, right, will be counted. Transport, yeah, so any, you know,

transportation, even our suppliers are doing to our sites will become the scope 3. Yeah, so those are the three that we have.

[Speaker 2] (16:52 - 17:09)

Next, we're going to talk about the scope 1. As you said, it's about operational efficiency and decarbonization. What renewable energy solutions are you prioritizing for these operations, and what's the timeline for the adoption?

[Speaker 1] (17:14 - 18:37)

So, okay, so the renewable energy solutions we're prioritizing for our own operations is electrification of our operations. We're trying our best to have that. We're trying to use renewable energy in some countries as an energy source for our field operations.

We're also looking at, so that's for our own operations, for our customers' operations as well. We're looking at geothermal, hydrogen, and CCUS, so we're trying our best to invest in geothermal and hydrogen. And then carbon storage is a kind of mitigation factor, right?

Carbon storage isn't an energy, but it's more to reduce emissions from your non-clean energy sources. What are our timelines for adoption? We want to reduce our scope 1 and scope 2 by 2025, a 30% reduction.

So by this year, we need a 30% reduction in scope 1 and scope 2 because that's easier to control, right? It's your own emissions, basically. We have a target of 50% by 2030, so in five years, we need to reduce by 50%.

And in 2050, we have to be net zero. That's our goal.

[Speaker 2] (18:39 - 18:47)

How do you measure and track progress on electrification and smart fuel management across different facilities?

[Speaker 1] (18:51 - 19:43)

Right now, we have a centralized carbon management platform and emissions quantification system where we look at the energy in all our facilities and offices globally and where we even connect the meters, right, to the system and we're looking at the emissions across our operations. All of this rolls up into our KPIs, into our sustainability reports, so we have a separate sustainability report that we have to produce every year. And that platform that we've built, the carbon management platform, where we track emissions, we've built it ourselves.

We not only use it for our operations, but we also sell the tool for our customers to use it. So that's how we're managing that at least.

[Speaker 2] (19:44 - 19:51)

Have you all set any milestones for reducing Scope 1 emission before your long-term net zero goals?

[Speaker 1] (19:51 - 20:07)

Yeah, so that's the one I mentioned now, right? So by 2025, we want a 30% reduction in Scope 1, 50% by 2030, and net zero by 2050. So yeah, those are key milestones this year, in five years, and in 25 years.

[Speaker 2] (20:08 - 20:18)

Can we also know what challenges have you faced in this transition to renewable energy in regions where SLB operates?

[Speaker 1] (20:18 - 21:57)

Okay, so our biggest challenges are grid constraints. So we have obviously the infrastructure sometimes lacking in the countries that we work. Reliability of these renewable energy sources, right, a lot of them require natural, obviously, generation of resources, and they aren't always available in the countries we work 24-7, which means you need to store energy, and storing energy for longer is quite tricky, if you know for renewable energy sources.

And permitting and regulatory complexity, right? We are also working in countries which are not chasing the energy transition as quickly as some other countries, right? So we are also, yeah, there aren't incentives, right?

In some countries, there's strong incentives to have cleaner energy. In some countries, there aren't strong incentives. So people don't want to pay the price.

Sometimes customers don't want to pay the price to have cleaner energy in some places. So we're working with those kind of constraints. And also, obviously, in some countries, it's not as capital intensive, right, to have clean energy there.

Whereas in other countries, it's easier. They have an infrastructure. It's not as capital intensive.

The government is subsidizing it. So that's where we struggle, I think, the most, is I think the permitting and regulatory complexity in the countries, yeah.

[Speaker 2] (21:58 - 22:11)

Now we're going to talk about Scope 3. As you mentioned, it's about suppliers, customer engagement. How are you encouraging suppliers to align with SLB's emission reduction targets?

[Speaker 1] (22:12 - 23:22)

Yeah, so Sanmashe engages suppliers through responsible supply chain programs. We are very strict, actually, about the suppliers that we onboard. And it's a very long process.

Sometimes it takes six months to a year to bring on a supplier. We have a lot of third-party disclosure processes, CDP supplier engagement, supplier assessments. Then if we find that they're the best supplier for what they do and they're still not able to reduce their environmental impact, we work with them and we collaborate together.

We even try to fund them to help them bring technology to reduce, to improve their measurements and emission reduction, basically, in general. So we normally report, there's a CDP supplier engagement A rating. So we normally look for that to improve.

It's suppliers which have a better rating for climate disclosure and performance. So we try our best to engage with those suppliers which have an A rating. And if they don't, if there's no supplier with that rating, we work to get them up to that rating.

[Speaker 2] (23:24 - 23:30)

Are there specific tools or platforms being used to improve digital emission transparency across the supply chain?

[Speaker 1] (23:35 - 24:19)

So, as I mentioned, we have this carbon management platform system that we use. And that's an emission quantification tool. So we calculate the GHG across the different parts of our operation.

But we also offer, as I said, we offer this digital sustainability and carbon management platform, not just internally, it's used across all our operations, but we also provide this to customers. And this helps us to drive, to get all the data we collect and transparency across the operations. And then to see the areas where the, we look at areas where the emissions are very high, right?

And we try to see what we can do to reduce specific locations. Yeah, so that's...

[Speaker 2] (24:22 - 24:37)

Can you also share with us an example of how SRB enables customer avoid emissions and how you quantify that impact?

[Speaker 1] (24:38 - 26:22)

Yeah. So, in general, I'll give you an example in a minute. In general, what we do is we try to develop technology.

We obviously produce hardware that people use in the field, in the operations, right? We try to make sure that the technology we produce is the most efficient way to, it uses the least electricity or energy, for example, and it produces the least emissions right now. So we've spent a lot of money in developing hardware technology that uses as little energy as possible and produces as little emission footprint as possible, right?

So that's our focus across the operations right now. We sometimes, for example, work in certain countries, for example, in the Middle East, where when we produce oil, always some gas comes out, if you're familiar with oil and gas, and the gas is useless in those. It's not used as a fuel source.

So what some of these countries do is they just flare the gas. They burn the gas on site, right? And that's very emission-heavy, right?

You produce a lot of emissions when you flare the gas on site. So what we do now is we collect that gas. So some of it we actually have in some countries, the technology where we collect the gas and we pump it back into the subsurface to avoid you emitting, to avoid you, and we're trying to do this quite cheaply because most people are economics-driven, right?

Most customers are economics-driven. So we try our best to be as cheap in actually pumping this gas back into the subsurface so that you're not increasing emissions by flaring. So we call this methane reduction technologies that we produce.

So we spend a lot of time on that.

[Speaker 2] (26:24 - 26:29)

What criteria do you use to select suppliers with strong sustainability performance?

[Speaker 1] (26:31 - 27:58)

Yeah, so I think I mentioned some of them, but basically we look for customers which have verified emissions reporting, right? Some don't. So we look that they have verified emissions reporting.

They have reports that we can actually have access to and view, right? That they have climate action plans, like a mission and a timeline like ours, right? They have alignment with science-based targets, right?

So they're not just arbitrary targets, right? But they're actually looking at the IPCC reports and they're aligning with those targets, the global targets that everyone is after. They have CDP or other disclosures.

Their HSE performance is good, right? So they don't have any incidents on site and things like this. And their capability to meet contractual low-carbon requirements.

So if they consistently don't meet low-carbon requirements while being on our operations, we replace the supplier. So we look for performance. It's okay to give those short answers, right?

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Redacted]

[Speaker 2] (28:27 - 28:40)

Now we're going to talk about reporting, innovation, and future plans. Can you tell us about how does SLB integrate sustainability performance into financial decision-making and reporting?

[Speaker 1] (28:43 - 29:46)

In terms of performance, our sustainability performance appears in SLB investors and annual reports, which is publicly available. Risk disclosures and capital allocation priorities.

So we kind of make sure we allocate a certain amount of capital towards our sustainability goals based on our reports.

The company links sustainability KPIs with strategic investments. Example, product development and low-carbon solutions. So based on those KPIs that we have for sustainability, we allocate a certain amount of budget to achieve those goals.

Like we said, by net zero by 2050, but the interim targets of 2025 and 2030 have to be achieved with some work, right? And we publish sustainability and annual financial reports that disclose these targets and progress publicly so that we're held accountable if we don't meet those goals. So I think that's generally how we do it.

Break 1

[Speaker 2] (0:00 - 2:28)

Are there plans to collaborate with local communities or government to accelerate decarbonization efforts?

[Speaker 1]

Yes, absolutely. So we work a lot with the community.

We, as I said, we invest in a lot of internships, PhDs, masters, projects, right? And now a lot that focus is not on oil and gas. Actually, I think a significant portion, and I don't know the exact number, but I would say at least in Norway here, where we operate, at least I could say based on my experience, at least 70% of those projects are for new energy or low carbon solutions, right? So we work a lot with STEM. We work with the universities.

We're constantly visiting universities looking for projects, right, to invest in. We also have nature and local projects in some countries. So we look at, you know, in South America, for example, we help with reforestation and things like this.

Water stewardship has been a very important thing for us because our operations consume a lot of water, right? So we've looked at reducing our water consumption across all operations, and we had a target that we reduced, I think, our water consumption at 9% in all facilities in the last couple of years, yeah, so which is a big improvement, right, in a short time. So that's, yeah, how we work with communities.

[Speaker 2]

Can we know what roles does innovation, for example, AI, IoT, or carbon capture play in your sustainability roadmap?

[Speaker 1]

So innovation is obviously very important to us because we're a technology company, right, especially digital technology.

Now you've heard with AI and all of these things, it's very important that we keep ahead of these technologies. When you enter the building, I forgot to take you on the right, we have

an innovation factory, a big space, where we actually collaborate with customers. So we bring customers in often, and we try to solve problems together, and we try to see where we can use AI and automation in our technologies to speed up workflows based on their problems and challenges.

[Speaker 1] (2:28 - 3:31)

So I'll take you down there later to show it to you. We use AI, for example, in a lot of our new digital technologies, and you can ask our engineers as well, they're using AI to basically speed up workflows. So users, for example, who use our subsurface technology to build models, they can now do it with just a few clicks.

Before it took months, right, to develop it, because they'd have to manually create each part of the workflow. So now what they do is we've created the workflow that can be automatically generated based on your input data. So we do that.

We also use a lot of automation and AI in our sensors, our hardware. As I said, we have a lot of hardware technology. So a lot of them, for example, some of our sensors, if the pressure is too high, for example, in the field, it can shut down automatically because it has an inbuilt sensor.

Before, in the past, you'd have to send an engineer to go physically shut it down. So stuff like that. So we've built a lot of this automation to reduce, also to make it faster, right, that we want to respond faster to problems.

[Speaker 1] (3:34 - 4:02)

And we also now, we're spending a lot of time building our new energy technologies, right? So carbon capture, we're spending, and I think my product is spending a lot of money on this year to develop brand new technologies. And in my product, because we're surveying operations, we're trying to be, as I said, very quick. So we're trying to use AI to automatically troubleshoot problems and then give response to the equipment to, you know, quickly respond.

(4:02 - 5:33)

So we're using a lot of this and we're also developing reports with AI. So we're using AI to automatically generate report for the company based on all of their data that they have to supply to the government. So that's, you know.

Internet of things as well. I mean, I think you're very familiar. We're using, because we are probably in the industry for 100 years, you know, and we have a huge stack of data for some clients that have been with us for ages.

So we're trying for certain clients that they can use their data, because they have so much data sitting somewhere. We're trying to see if we can help them use their data to make better decisions, right? So that they can learn from their own data. That's also something.

[Speaker 2]

How do you ensure transparency and credibility in your emission reporting? For example, through third party verification?

[Speaker 1]

Yeah, so all of the sustainability reports that we generate, we use accounting methodologies that protocol, GHG protocol, right? And we always have a third party verification disclosure process. Example, CDP has to verify, has to come in and verify. But we also have a lot of audits, that ISO audits and things like that, that come into our facilities to audit a lot of, I've participated in an audit before as well, where they even check your laptop and they, you know, they see all of your infrastructure and they do random checks of employees as well.

(5:34 - 5:53)

So to make sure that we are kind of, yeah, not fraudulently, yeah, claiming certain emissions credit. So the third party verification is big for us. [REDACTED]

[Speaker 2] (9:29 - 12:45)

Okay. Okay. Now we're going to talk about the project.

Can you name one or more policies your firm faces that could change its P&L in the next 24 months or over a longer time frame?

[Speaker 1]

Okay. So my challenge is that I need for my application or my project to be successful. I'm not a commercial product yet.

We're not in the market yet. There's a commercial product. So we have a race to get to the market next year, the same at this time.

So we need to be a commercial product by this time next year, which means we need to onboard clients soon after, right? Because when you bring a product to market, you need to make sure that you have lined up customers already, right? That are willing to use your solution pretty quickly, or you're spending too much money to keep it without any revenue generation on the shelf. So my challenge will be first, because we've developed from scratch a tool from February this year. So I have less than a year and a half to get to market, which is a big challenge, being a fully commercial tool to the market in a year and a half, if you're familiar with that product life cycle.

And also, we need to make sure that there's enough carbon storage projects in operation by then, right? So we also face external challenges where a lot of projects are deciding whether to go forward or not for carbon storage. And many of them are taking decision not to pursue the carbon storage project because of economic constraints. And so, yeah, we're going to face that challenge of having enough customers who are going into operations at that time and us bringing the product to market.

I think that's going to be our biggest challenge that will affect definitely the P&L of my product.

[Speaker 2]

You did talk about a little bit of the challenge, but the next question is, what grand challenges have the company faced in developing sustainable innovation?

[Speaker 1]

Okay, so because I'm on the carbon capture and storage side, I think our biggest challenge is scaling the new technology to meet industrial levels, right? And lowering the technology costs. CCS, as you're familiar with, is mostly waste disposal.

We don't generate revenue from producing an energy source, right? So we need to be as cheap as possible, right? We can't have the same cost as an oil and gas operation. So we need to make sure that you're able to scale the technology, which makes the technology cheaper, right, as well? Because, yeah, once you're able to do things cheaply, then it's more usable, right? And aligning with the customer investment cycles, so that's also a challenge. Because we have a race to net zero, we need to bring products out pretty quickly.

We can't say, okay, we're going to do R&D for 10 years, and then we're going to bring a product to market because we know most companies have to reduce their emissions by 2025, 2030, and then 2050. We need to bring the technology to help them pretty quickly. So we're working on cycles that we haven't worked on before, right? Like bringing products to market very quickly.

(12:46 - 16:58)

Also, there's a lot of regulatory uncertainty in some countries. Like in Asia, for example, the regulations are behind. So we're waiting for regulations to come in place to make carbon capture and storage more lucrative, right? And then integrating these tools with legacy operations, right? It's quite difficult, right? So we have a lot of challenges.

A lot of clients don't want to move to the cloud or to digital solutions. They still want a manual approach for things. Even if we can give it to them cheaper, it's just that humans don't like the process of change sometimes, and it's hard to implement that.

So I think those are the biggest challenges we face.

[Speaker 2]

Can we know how did the project create value for stakeholders?

[Speaker 1]

Okay, so my current project is still in the development phase. So we're not creating a large value yet, right? We're scheduled to create value next year.

But what we are doing right now is we are working with some partners. So we have a pilot, for example, that we're working on in Taiwan with the company. So we're helping them to test our technology on their operation and see.

So we're kind of de-risking our technology and helping them at the same time. So we're running a test pilot together to see if our technology really helps them to reduce the, you know, to make them more operationally efficient and reduce their emissions, you know, by being more efficient in general. But next year we'll drive more value, obviously, for stakeholders.

This year, early next year, we're spending money more than generating value.

[Speaker 2]

How do you differentiate your project or product or technology from competitors? What do you see as your key competitive advantage?

[Speaker 1]

Okay, so I think our biggest competitive advantage is being the global leader for technology in the sector, right? So we have a reputation. So we ride a lot on our brand, right? So that's our biggest advantage, right? Having that brand name.

Like for a phone, you buy Apple, right? So for SLB, we're known as the market leader for technology and especially subsurface, right? Oil and gas has been subsurface driven, and CCS is also subsurface driven, right? A lot, like at least 90% of the projects we're injecting CO2 underground, which is our main strength, right, for technology drilling wells and things like that. So in that way, we have that market leadership. We have a reputation of drilling and being able to drill securely, safely, right? We have less incidents on operations and things like that.

So on that side, we have that reputation. For digital solutions as well, we are very famous, right, for producing digital solutions. What we do as well, our biggest differentiator is being able to connect our digital solutions to the hardware in the field, because we have both of them that belong to us, right? A lot of digital companies, they are dependent on the hardware from another company, right, which is harder, because then you have to collaborate.

When you own the hardware and the digital technology, it's easier for you to integrate, right, internally than externally. So I think that's one of our big things. Because we're a global player, we work in so many countries, right? We have this global deployment scale.

So we have the ability, we have offices everywhere, right? We have local presence, which means we can pretty quickly get you a solution in any part of the world, right? And we have a partner ecosystem that we've been working on for the last many years, especially in the digital side. For example, we're partners with Microsoft, right? So my technology is fully based on Microsoft technology on top of Microsoft and Google, right? We have a separate partnership with Google as well. And we have a partnership with other, like for mine, for the data platform, I have a partnership with a company called Cognite, which is quite popular for operations.

(16:59 - 18:23)

So we have a lot of key partnerships that we've been working on, which means that when they sign on a customer, we have access to that customer as well, right, which is a differentiator for us. And we find it easier to get partnerships when you're a reputed company, right, in the business. And on top of that, because we have the broad portfolio of tools, we're able to connect each of these tools.

So we're able to provide almost the entire value chain to a customer. They don't have to go to five different customers to get their operations sorted. They can say, can you just handle the whole supply chain? So I think that's a big differentiator.

Many companies don't like, especially for CCS, they don't like to have a contract with five different companies. It makes it expensive to manage, right, internally if you have to have five different contracts and you have to have a HR department and a procurement department that handles all of this. So I think that's our biggest differentiation.

[Speaker 2]

Does SLB engage with local communities, particularly on environmental initiatives?

[Speaker 1]

So I think I touched on this earlier. So we obviously work with, we have community investments, we do. So we have some charitable works that we do in different parts of, in different countries that we operate in.

(18:24 - 20:01)

STEM programs. So we, for example, fund even education of women for STEM education in Africa, for example. We have a massive program for that.

And as I said, internships globally, we are, I think, one of the biggest internship generator in this industry. And then I mentioned also water stewardship. So we've been working, our last few years, we've been working heavily on water stewardship and circularity.

So water stewardship is, you know, 9% less water consumption in facilities, as I said. And we try to recycle water as well. So when we use water, we try to recycle it and use it again, rather than, you know, constantly getting water from freshwater sources.

So we look for this closed water systems. And circularity is the five-hour framework that you're probably familiar with. Reduce, reuse, refurbish, remanufacture, and recycle.

So we're trying our best across our operations to reduce, reuse, refurbish, remanufacture, and recycle. So we don't just like, you know, when a tool is not working, we try to repair it, for example, and use it again, or use at least the raw parts we don't throw away, because our tools use a lot of resources, right, like metals, things like that. So we're trying our best.

And in 2024, for example, we diverted more than 200,000 metric tons of material from the landfill. So instead of going to the landfill, we used it, we used it in our operations. So that was something.

(20:03 - 25:25)

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED] Yeah, so we have, obviously, we had like 30 internships, right, this year. So we kind of get a lot of internships from, not just actually NTNU, any of the universities, because we also go to Sweden, I think probably.

So we get from all of Europe as well. Yeah, so we get a lot of internships. We, to be honest, here in Norway, we don't do as much work for water stewardship because we don't use so much water on our facilities.

You can imagine Norway is quite efficient in, that's why Norway is a hard one for us because they're already quite efficient sustainability-wise, right? Like if you go to like some of our facilities in the Middle East or Africa, they're using a lot of resources. You can imagine there's no regulation to stop you from doing bad things, right? So that's where you can improve a lot because you're so bad in the first place that to reduce, you know, like your water consumption, because you probably use so much water, you can, it's easy to do that. But in Norway, if you ask me, like, oh probably we use, we already don't use much water because the government doesn't allow you to just take water from water sources and edit the operations, right? In Norway, they make you reduce, reuse, recycle.

You can't even throw out your waste, like metal waste, into the regular bin, right, for example. Imagine if you had these huge equipments, we couldn't just throw it in the trash. Norway will find you like crazy for this.

So I think, yeah, it's quite hard to make that kind of sustainability impact. But I mean, I know for sure that we're doing a lot of carbon storage projects. Our biggest market is Scandinavia.

So in that sense, yeah, and we have a lot of wind, where we're using a lot of our technology for wind energy.

[Speaker 2]

Did the project promote or initiate any environmental engagement?

[Speaker 1]

Okay, yeah, so I think I mentioned a lot of, you know, environment engagement, the company does as a whole, right? And my project being, if you know SLB, we're kind of, the policy is enforced on every project.

So if the company is going after certain initiatives, every project is forced to go after those initiatives. You're not allowed to divert from the general company policy. So, for example, I have to use suppliers that are vetted.

So I have to use Microsoft, for example, for my cloud infrastructure, because they're vetted by the company and they have a good sustainability record, right? So I'm engaging with only suppliers that have very good sustainability record. What we've also done is we've engaged with regulators. So I've spoken to a lot of government bodies and regulators on how we can help them with their regulations, right? So they ask us what technology is available, for example, for different parts of the value chain, and we give them information about what's possible and what's not possible for people to track, for example, in the operations.

And then we work with them to, you know, they tell us actually we need a technology to track the CO2 emissions at this part of the value chain, because there's nothing that's tracking that. So then we have to develop that technology with them. So we are working even with local regulations, right, bodies.

We actually work in Norway with the regulator, for example, and they even fund, so the Norwegian government is even funding one of our products here to make sure that it's fit

for carbon storage, for example. So, yeah, we're trying our best to, you know, work with these engagements.

[Speaker 2]

So based on your most recent projects, what were the key outcomes of that project?

[Speaker 1]

Okay.

It can be a finished one. Yeah, okay. So I brought last year, at least, I shouldn't say I, the team, the team brought a product to market.

(25:25 - 28:10)

So this is the second product that I'm working on as a product manager. The previous product was brought to market last year to help companies to screen large areas of land, right, to see where they can start their carbon storage project. So we look at the subsurface, we see what's the best location to have your subsurface project, you know, initiated.

So the tool that we developed was helping them to look at large areas and rank them in order of what's the most suitable based on the different criteria. Proximity to infrastructure, you know, where the conditions are favorable, is it far enough from the community that it won't impact the community, for example. So this product is now a commercial product available for clients to use, and we've had a lot of interest from clients who are trying.

So we've done a lot of projects with this. In the last year, we've done at least 10 projects with clients, I think two of them in Scandinavia, using the product to help the company to decide where to start their carbon storage project, basically. So yeah, so that's, I think, one of the key outcomes that we've actually used the product and made a decision with the client together on where the carbon storage project should be located.

[Speaker 2]

Next, what was the impact of the project on the financial economic aspect of the company?

[Speaker 1]

Okay, so that particular project, for example, we worked on at least, as I said, 10 projects in the last two years. We've done more in three, four years, but the last two years, and we've generated quite a significant revenue from that.

So yeah, something like eight million dollars, maybe, in revenue using that particular product for our company. But for a customer, we enable them to basically make the right decision, right? So you can't quantify that easily, but for example, we help them to firstly speed up their process, so they do it faster. So they don't use, like, for example, to do a survey to understand where to start your carbon storage project, will sometimes take two years for a company.

We try to speed them up to do it with digital technology in six months. So they save at least on a year and a half of resources and they can make the decisions faster. Yeah, so that's, I think, that's it.

(28:13 - 29:59)

And what about the trade-offs, for example, conflicts between social goals and profitability? Yeah, so short-term margins versus long-term strategic positioning, right?

Yeah, so this is a tough one, right, because we've seen many times that companies take, you know, everyone has to look at their top line, right, or their bottom line, right, of their financial sheets, and sometimes making environmental or socially responsible decisions can impact those top lines. A lot of companies, they make a trade-off, they go after short-term profit, right, rather than long-term strategic goals or for the greater good of the society in general, right, and we see that often, but generally what we see is when there's good regulations in the country that incentivize you, right, like in high-tax countries like Norway, for example, they allow you to get back some of your taxes, a lot of it if you do ESG initiatives, right, so we see that actually regulations can play a big impact in companies not having to trade off short-term goals versus long-term, you know, impact on the society, so I think that's, yeah, so that's why we try to, yeah, try to engage with, yeah, clients in these countries, and also we're trying to get those clients to help scale the technology because they have the incentive to do so, they can help you to scale the technology to bring it cheaper to countries, for example, in Asia, who can't afford that, right, so if we can make the technology scale out faster and cheaper, then it's countries that don't have the regulation in place or the economics to support it can get it for cheaper, right, and then maybe they don't have to make the trade-off, right, later, yeah, so that's where we're focusing at the moment.

Break 2

[Speaker 2] (0:00 - 2:07)

So, the next question was about conflicts, so you already answered that part, so the next question would be, how do you relate and balance activities that create economic value with those that create social value in your company?

[REDACTED]

[Speaker 2] (7:35 - 7:44)

How do you relate and balance activities that create economic value with those that create social value in your company?

[Speaker 1] (7:47 - 11:06)

Yeah, so to balance economic and social value, an organization like SLB, we're large, right, can integrate social impact into their co-business strategy, right, through partnerships, business models, and a focus on measurable social outcomes alongside financial metrics. So what we make sure always is that we always have to, in our KPIs for the year, for example, we have to have certain social metrics, like you have to, like within the company, if you say in your company, I have to, for example, do learnings, right, I have to promote knowledge sharing, a certain amount of knowledge sharing, you have to make sure you're passing on knowledge, officially mentoring people in the company, so that way at least you make sure that you have a social impact. I, for example, because I'm in digital sustainability, the rest of this building is predominantly focused, majority, let's say, of the operation here is oil and gas technology, so my job is to make sure that everyone knows, you know, we have a social responsibility, right, for digital sustainability, so I try my best also to educate the, yeah, to make sure that they know that we're developing technology to try to get more people invested in those things.

So we, yeah, so I have, yeah, try my best to also impart knowledge basically as a slightly senior more resource than some of the younger professionals here. And then also we try, obviously, here in this office, we're very good with environmental and social impact, for example, because, as I said, recycling, you know, we make sure that everything in our office, we don't, you know, discard office waste, just, you know, into a regular bin, everything is well sorted, taken to recycle plants, and we do that, we make sure that we have a community of volunteers here that make sure that we do that, we even go to the recycle plant and make sure our waste is sorted, and once, two, three times a year, our electrical waste will be brought to the recycle, so our social impact, we try to keep our footprint low.

We do cleanups, beach cleanups, things like that, those kind of initiatives in the office, we organize the volunteers together to do that, so those kind of things. So we try at least our best to make sure that we aren't just going after economics, but we use our resources to also give a good social impact, right, and you can use work hours to do those things, so they don't have to do it on the weekends, they can do a beach cleanup during their work hours, right, so things like that, so that's how we, I think, we're quite good here at balancing that. Also, as I said, we take internships, and they always, every intern has a mentor, so the mentor has to provide mentorship a certain number of hours, right, so they're using their workday to make sure that the student is well catered to, well mentored, and stuff like that, yeah, so I think that's how we do it here.

[REDACTED]

[Speaker 2] (15:47 - 16:02)

Now, for the extra questions. Could you give us an example of government regulation that incentivize you to prioritize long-term sustainability over short-term profits?

[Speaker 1] (16:03 - 17:42)

Okay. So, I can talk about two of our biggest markets for carbon storage, at least, which is the US and EU. So, the US has this Inflation Reduction Act and a 45-Q tax credit law, which puts a price on carbon storage per ton, roughly at \$80 to \$180, depending on how you capture the carbon dioxide.

Because they put a price on carbon dioxide, it directly incentivizes. It's like a price per barrel of oil that you produce, right? So, basically, the government gives you money for every ton of CO2 that you store, which is very beneficial, right?

Because it's normally waste. No one wants to store CO2, right? So, in order to incentivize, they actually put a price that's very high, right?

And so, that directly incentivizes. It gives you the economic structure you need, right, to have a carbon storage project. So, that's in the US.

They've done it that way. In EU, they have an emissions trading scheme, if you're familiar with the ETS, where you can trade your emissions for tax rebates, right? So, that also incentivizes you because you pay a lot of taxes for all the emissions that you produce on your operations.

So, you can basically get back some of that if you do carbon storage. So, it actually, again, puts a kind of price on carbon dioxide. So, you use that to drive your economics, right?

Because if companies are just going to spend from their pockets, right, to store CO2, they won't do it. They need some incentive for it to be economic, right, for them. So, those are two very important pieces of regulation that help accelerate carbon dioxide efforts.

[Speaker 2] (17:43 - 17:58)

The next question is what's something that you could do to further improve your sustainability aspects of your project or in the company in general that you have yet to do it?

[Speaker 1] (17:59 - 20:07)

So, on our project, I think we could reduce travel between the teams. Our team is split, you know, is in many different continents. We're split between continents and countries.

So, I think to reduce our sustainability impact, we could travel less, to be honest. Nowadays, everything is possible, right, online. Remote working is, like, quite easy.

So, I think we're still traveling quite a lot between countries. I'm traveling next week, for example, to the UK for in-person reporting workshop. But, yeah, so I think we should maybe consider that's something we could do, I think, to get a direct impact soon.

We, as a company, as a whole, I think commuting is a big, right, burden on our emissions a lot, even nowadays, especially in some countries where our offices are maybe very far from,

they're in industrial areas, right, they're very far from residential areas. So, people are commuting a lot to get to the site. We should incentivize by maybe, for them to take public transport, right, by maybe paying for the public transport, right, as a company.

Maybe you say, okay, you have a certain allowance if you're on the public transport, if you use public transport. But if you don't, we don't give you the allowance to avoid, you know, to make people use their car less, right, or something like this. I think this has been, many companies have done that.

They've incentivized people commuting using public transport. I don't know why a company hasn't, yeah, invested in that personally. I think, and some companies also in cities where they have like an office in a big city, like maybe also we have in Den Haag, for example, and they actually pay for bike, for a bike, for an employee to have a bike, right, and they have the facilities in place for you to have, you know, if you have an electric bike, you can charge it and stuff like this.

Yeah, we don't, this is all for us. It's all based on the employee, right, like it's the responsibility is on the employee. But I think the corporate could take more responsibility for that, right, yeah.

That's, I think, something we could do.

[Speaker 3] (20:08 - 20:11)

I think that there's one other thing that the Netherlands, they do it.

[Speaker 1] (20:12 - 20:12)

Yeah.

[Speaker 3] (20:14 - 20:16)

Incentivize employees to take public transport.

[Speaker 1] (20:17 - 20:59)

Yeah, exactly, yeah, exactly. Yeah, and so like, for example, Germany and Netherlands, they allow you to take it out from your taxes. So if you can prove that you're using public transport a lot, so it's not the companies, but that is the, you know, you pay so much tax, that it's okay if you're using this much public transport, you can, you get tax rebate back for that.

But Norway's not doing that, for example. So, yeah, they could do that. If Norway doesn't do that, at least the company can say, actually, we'll refund you if you use public transport.

Because if you don't make things economic, people don't do it, right. People, yeah, people, that's what affects their own pocket, right, generally, yeah. So I think that would be a good thing to start.

[Speaker 3] (21:00 - 21:08)

And I'm just wondering if the company have any, like, rules about the home office?

[Speaker 1] (21:08 - 22:11)

So in that, I think we've implemented quite well. We have two, we call it, we have a program called Blue Flex, which requires you to be in office two to three days a week, based on your team and your location. So we've, that's quite good.

And that's worldwide for us, for all facilities, except for ones that require the engineer, obviously, full time, right, on site. But for, like, especially offices, it's two to three days a week. And they also give flexibility to work fully remote for some people, like, from home.

Especially if they require less, like, for younger professionals, they require more handholding, right, like, more mentoring in person. So it's harder sometimes. But for experienced staff who don't, who have jobs that don't require them to be in office, you can work almost fully remote, and they're quite flexible like that.

So we try those things. So I think that we've done well. But I think the commuting part, we don't incentivize people to commute by public transport, even in Norway.

Yeah, which is, you know, not great, I think.

[Speaker 3] (22:12 - 22:15)
That was really useful. Yeah.

[Speaker 1] (22:23 - 22:24)
Yeah, any other questions? We're good?

[Speaker 3] (22:25 - 22:27)
Yeah, we're good. That was really useful.

[Speaker 1] (22:28 - 22:31)
No, thank you for that. I wish I could have done better.